

Detailed Response to Reviewers

Dear Editor,

We have carefully revised our manuscript to address all the reviewers' comments. The following tables include an item by item response to each reviewer comment on our paper entitled "A Multi-Objective Optimization Procedure for Solving the High-Order Epistasis Detection Problem" (ESWA-D-19-02608R2).

Best regards.

Reviewer #1	
Reviewer's comments	Authors' response
The article presented an implementation of a multi-objective optimization algorithm, based on a modification of NSGA-II, to solve a problem associated to spring process focusing in large amount of data. The main idea was to solve the problem in reasonable time. Considerable improvements in the article were performed in this new version.	Thanks for your comment.
Just minor corrections are suggested. In this case, some typos can be found in the manuscript, see: Page 4, last paragraph: "31,341 SNPs under a epistasis size of 8 loci" -> "31,341 SNPs under an epistasis size of 8 loci"	This typo has been corrected.
In all descriptions the multiplication operator used is "x" except in: page 9 2nd topic: 2 * popSize page 13 Eq. (9): $mutRange = N \cdot (mutFactor)/100$ The reviewer recommend to change the operator following the same pattern.	We have replaced "*" and "." by "x" in the places indicated by the reviewer and we have revised the whole paper to ensure that we employ always the "x" operator.
The reason why authors did not implement NSGA-III, which was suggested in the first revision, was well addressed and justified.	Thanks for your comment.

A Multi-Objective Optimization Procedure for Solving the High-Order Epistasis Detection Problem

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Abstract

There are multiple research works that establish a relationship between Single Nucleotide Polymorphisms (SNPs) and complex diseases. In many cases, these diseases are caused by the interaction of two or more SNPs (epistasis). Therefore, it is important to identify which SNPs lead to the emergence of diseases. However, this problem gets harder when the epistasis order and the number of SNPs in the dataset under study are increased. To tackle this problem, this work presents an implementation of a multi-objective optimization algorithm with a problem-aware offspring process. Furthermore, due to the large amount of data in the SNPs datasets, we have also parallelized this algorithm. We experimentally validate the quality of the proposal under epistasis sizes of 2, 5, and 8 loci, although the application is not limited to those values. Moreover, a thorough comparative study of biological performance with six state-of-the-art methods has been conducted, obtaining better results than all the other biological methods. Our results confirm that, using the proposed approach, large datasets with high-order epistasis sizes can be processed in reasonable time, obtaining solutions of good quality. According to the literature review performed until the acceptance of this article, there are no other authors' works that can process epistasis sizes above 6 loci in large datasets.

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1. Introduction

Epistasis is defined as the interaction of two or more loci¹ in the presence of a specific phenotype²(Rieger et al. (1968)). Epistasis is responsible for many traits of animals and plants. When an individual shows epistasis between SNPs³ (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism), these interactions can lead to the emergence of complex diseases like diabetes, Alzheimer’s or Parkinson’s (Rogus et al. (2008), Wanga et al. (2016)). This is the reason why multiple works in GWAS (Genome-Wide Association Study) put especial emphasis on finding these gene-to-gene interactions. Nevertheless, there are two fundamental problems in this context: the first one is to establish the epistasis size, that is, how many SNPs interact in the epistasis, and the second one is the huge number of combinations that this interaction order can imply. More specifically, the number of combinations that a k -order epistasis can generate when considering N SNPs is shown in Equation (1). For instance, a dataset with $N = 31,341$ implies more than 47×10^{30} different combinations for $k = 8$.

$$\binom{N}{k} = \frac{N!}{k! \times (N - k)!} \quad (1)$$

There are some works that solve the epistasis detection problem by using exhaustive search methods, which proceed by computing all the possible SNP combinations for a dataset. However, this approach leads to the problem that, when the number of SNPs in the dataset is high, the time needed to finish the exhaustive search is very huge. For this reason, parallel hardware architectures are used to reduce execution time. We can find works like Kam-Thong et al. (2010) that compute, through a two-step process, the difference in Pearson’s correlation coefficients between controls and cases across all possible SNP pairs using Graphical Processing Units (GPUs). Wan et al. (2013) proposes a method to test epistasis in GWAS data also using GPUs. In Gonzalez-Dominguez et al. (2015), the problem is tackled by using 128

¹A locus (plural loci) is the fixed position of a gene or a genetic marker on a chromosome.

²Expression of the genotype or genetic information from a particular organism.

³A variation in a single nucleotide that occurs at a specific position in the genome.

Field Programmable Gate Arrays (FPGAs) and 4 GPUs to reduce execution time. Finally, Weeks et al. (2018) proposes an approach for clusters environments based on MPI and OpenMP, employing 126 computing nodes each one containing 8 cores and 2 Xeon Phi.

All these previous works process relationships of two loci, but other works can be found that employ parallel architectures and exhaustive search on three loci: Wienbrandt et al. (2017) proposes an exhaustive tool for third-order interaction detection on a genome-wide scale that uses a heterogeneous architecture composed of a GPU and an FPGA accelerator within a desktop PC. González-Domínguez & Schmidt (2015) implements a GPU-accelerated tool to exhaustively search for interactions among all marker-triples of a given case-control dataset. In addition, Kässens et al. (2015) discusses how a hardware-assisted design can perform third-order epistasis analyses with up-to-date FPGA technology. Li (2017) combines exhaustive search, Matlab, parallelism, and two objectives with epistasis sizes of 2 and 3 loci, but even with all this, it needs more than 7,000 seconds for processing a 1,000 SNPs dataset using 3 loci. However, all these works can only process epistasis sizes of 2 or 3 loci (even when using hardware coprocessors and parallelism, the huge number of combinations makes unfeasible the application of exhaustive searches for more than 3 loci). For instance, it is stated in Kässens et al. (2015) that, for a dataset of 500,000 SNPs and 3 loci, more than eight years of computation are needed to complete the search.

One extended alternative to the exhaustive search is to use procedures that remove all non-significant loci based on single-locus tests. Under this approach, we can find works like (Crawford et al. (2017)), whose goal is to identify candidate variants by testing marginal epistatic effects, thus avoiding explicit searches for pairwise interactions. Mathew et al. (2018) applies some techniques for dimensionality reduction in order to identify two-way and three-way epistasis. Leem et al. (2014) and Jünger et al. (2017) run k-means clustering algorithm on the set of all SNPs to select the top m SNPs by the score (reducing the total number of SNPs to $k \times m$). However, these methods remove a huge number of SNPs, leading to the problem of losing potentially important SNPs.

Finally, a new alternative is emerging in recent years: the use of genetic and evolutionary algorithms (Niel et al. (2015)). Genetic and evolutionary algorithms are very powerful tools that can be used for solving problems in very diverse study areas, as can be trading (Goldkamp & Dehghanimohammadabadi (2019)), medicine (Mitra et al. (2018)), and biology (Gohardani et al. (2019)). In this way, we can find single-objective implementations, which employ only one objective function to determine the quality of a solu-

tion, and multi-objective implementations, which use, at least, two different objective functions to determine the quality of a solution. As examples of single-objective methods, we have *AntEpiSeeker* (Wang et al. (2010)), based on the Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) algorithm, or *CSE* (Aflakparast et al. (2014)), which uses a modified Cuckoo Search algorithm. As for multi-objective approaches, we can find *FHSA-SED* (Tuo et al. (2016)), based on the Harmony Search Algorithm (HSA), or *MACOED* (Jing & Shen (2015)), which implements a multi-objective version of ACO. As Jing & Shen (2015) point out, the single-objective approximations of this problem are based on a single correlation model or objective function for SNPs and disease. Due to the complexity and divergent preferences of different disease models, these approximations work worse than those based on more objective functions (Jing & Shen (2015)). This is the reason that justifies the interest in tackling this problem with multi-objective optimization.

A complete survey about methods dedicated to epistasis detection can be found in Niel et al. (2015), and Wei et al. (2014) shows a review about the epistasis detection problem including the methods described above.

In the present work, we apply the fast Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) (Deb et al. (2002)) to solve the high-order epistasis detection problem in a multi-objective context, validating it by using three different epistasis interaction sizes: 2, 5, and 8 loci. We adopt the same objective functions as in Jing & Shen (2015) (*MACOED*) and, to effectively conduct the optimization process, we propose an offspring generation process aimed at improving NSGA-II. According to the literature review performed until the acceptance of this article, there are no other works that can solve the epistasis detection problem with more than 6 loci in large datasets. On the other hand, our proposal is validated up to 8 loci relationships, but it is not limited to that value.

Moreover, we have parallelized the proposed method to reduce execution time, allowing the efficient execution of our approach in datasets with large numbers of SNPs. As an illustration, our proposal is able to conduct, in only 17.4 minutes, the analysis of a dataset of 31,341 SNPs under an epistasis size of 8 loci. In order to measure the quality of our proposal, we have performed a biological study comparing our implementation with six state-of-the-art biological methods for epistasis detection by means of four well-known metrics: power, recall, precision and f-measure. These metrics show the accuracy of one method from detecting the disease-causing models and its tolerance against false positives and false negatives. Our proposal achieves better results than the other biological methods in all these metrics, demonstrating its quality in the epistasis detection problem.

This paper is organized as follows: section 2 describes the tackled problem, detailing afterwards the proposed approach in section 3. The obtained results and the comparisons with previous works are shown and discussed in sections 4 and 5. Finally, we highlight conclusions and future research directions in section 6.

2. Problem Definition

Given the genotype data of a set of samples, which are classified as cases (samples with the disease) and controls (samples without the disease), our multi-objective optimization approach generates a set of combinations of k SNPs (being k the epistasis size) that cause the disease. Since each SNP is a value between 0 and $N - 1$ (being N the number of SNPs in the samples dataset), a solution is given by a list of k non-repeated sorted values between 0 and $N - 1$.

The evaluation of each solution is based on two objective functions: The first function measures the relationship between the SNP subsets and the disease status, and the second one measures the likelihood and complexity of the model. Considering these two functions, this work formulates the epistasis detection as a multi-objective optimization problem, as described in Equation (2). The upper and lower limits of each x component define the *decision space* of the problem (Ω). In our case, the objective functions y_1 and y_2 define a two-dimensional space known as *objective space* (R^2). Thus, for each solution $x = \{x_1, \dots, x_k\} \in \Omega$, there is a corresponding point $z = \{y_1(x), y_2(x)\}$ in the objective space.

$$\begin{aligned} \min \quad & \{y_1(x), y_2(x)\} \\ \text{subject to} \quad & x \in \Omega \\ & \forall i, j \in [1, k], i \neq j \Rightarrow x_i \neq x_j \\ & \forall i, j \in [1, k], i < j \Rightarrow x_i < x_j, \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where a solution x is a vector of k decision variables and k is the number of loci in the epistasis.

The following subsections detail the two adopted objective functions.

2.1. Bayesian K2 Score

The first objective function (y_1) is built upon a Bayesian Network. A Bayesian Network (Gopnik & Tenenbaum (2007)) is a probabilistic graphical model that represents a directed acyclic graph, in which a set of random variables are denoted by a set of nodes and their conditional dependencies are denoted by a set of edges. In our case, a logarithmic version of a Bayesian

Network is employed in order to reduce the computational complexity of the factorial operations used in a traditional Bayesian Network (Jing & Shen (2015)). Equation (3) shows the logarithmic version of the Bayesian Network employed in this work.

$$y_1 = \sum_{i=1}^I \left(\sum_{b=1}^{r_i+1} \log(b) - \sum_{j=1}^J \sum_{d=1}^{r_{ij}} \log(d) \right), \quad (3)$$

where I is the combinatorial number of SNP nodes with different values ($I = 3^k$ in this case, since the value of SNP nodes can be ‘0’ - homozygous major allele -, ‘1’ - heterozygous allele - and ‘2’ - homozygous minor allele), J is the state number of the disease node y (in this case, y can be 0 for controls and 1 for cases, so $J = 2$), r_i is the number of cases with SNP nodes taking the i th combination and r_{ij} is the number of cases where the disease node takes the j th state and its parents take the i th combination.

Therefore, the y_1 function is a measurement of the relationship between SNP nodes and disease nodes. The lower the value of y_1 , the stronger the association between the SNP subset and the disease will be.

2.2. Akaike Information Criterion (AIC)

The second objective function used in this work (y_2) is the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) (Akaike (1973)) of maximum likelihood for a certain model of epistasis interaction (Equation (4)). More specifically, in this work an additive-interactive model (North et al. (2005)) is employed in order to balance the computational feasibility and accuracy of our algorithm. AIC score is a probabilistic measurement that reflects both the model’s fitness to the dataset (lik) and its complexity (d).

$$y_2 = -2 \log(lik) + 2d, \quad (4)$$

where lik is the model’s maximum likelihood and d is the number of free parameters (being $d = k + 2$).

To calculate the maximum likelihood of the model, we employ binary logistic regression (Freedman (2009)). This kind of logistic regression can estimate the probability of a binary response based on one or more predictor variables. It allows identifying if the presence of a risk factor increases the probability of a given outcome by a specific factor. Equation (5) shows the logistic regression formula for k loci.

$$lik = \log \frac{r}{1-r} = \mu + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i x_i + \xi \prod_{i=1}^k x_i, \quad (5)$$

Table 1: Pareto optimal solutions obtained using the 31,341 SNPs and 8 loci as epistasis size. The first eight columns are the SNPs included in each solution and the last two columns are the values of the two objective functions.

		SNPs forming the solution						y_1	y_2
1 st	2 nd	3 rd	4 th	5 th	6 th	7 th	8 th		
4866	6739	12426	13256	17574	23629	24360	27121	69.02	222.40
4866	6739	12426	13256	16664	23802	24360	24429	69.63	154.72
4866	6739	12426	13256	20490	24360	24429	27121	70.33	145.46
4866	6739	12426	13256	16664	22882	24360	24429	70.46	145.30
4866	6739	12426	13256	23629	24360	24429	27121	70.59	138.25
4866	6739	12426	13256	22882	23629	24360	27121	70.88	134.70
792	6739	13256	14386	21522	23629	25044	27121	71.16	131.55
4866	6739	7174	14380	19983	22882	23629	27121	72.31	127.58
4866	6739	7174	13256	19983	22882	23629	27121	72.62	126.94
4866	6739	12426	13256	20187	23629	27121	30408	73.97	111.51
4866	6739	12426	13256	20187	23629	24360	27121	74.21	109.26
4866	6739	12426	13256	19547	20187	23629	27121	74.63	106.81
4866	6739	12426	13256	20187	22882	23629	27121	75.59	104.66
4866	6739	12426	13256	20187	23629	25044	27121	76.24	100.37
4866	6739	12426	13256	20187	21859	23629	27121	78.51	99.29
4866	6739	8142	12426	13256	20187	23629	27121	79.81	96.99
4866	6722	6739	12426	13256	20187	23629	27121	83.66	96.88
6739	12426	13256	14386	20187	23629	27121	30310	84.04	94.22
5572	6739	13256	14386	20187	23629	27121	30310	88.17	92.87
5572	6739	13256	15421	19547	20187	22003	27121	91.39	92.73
6739	13256	14386	15421	20187	22003	27121	28839	92.49	88.80
5572	6739	13256	14386	20187	22003	27121	28839	94.44	85.57
5572	6739	7174	13256	20187	22003	27121	30310	95.03	84.98
4998	5572	6739	13256	20187	22003	26309	27121	96.95	84.94

where x_i ($\forall i \in [1, k]$) are the loci, μ is the mean term which depends on population prevalence and sample sizes, the β_i values ($\forall i \in [1, k]$) model additive effects at each locus, ξ models interactive effects among all loci, and r denotes the conditional probability $p(y = 1|x_i, \forall i \in [1, k])$ ($y = 1$ denotes a case sample).

Therefore, the lower the value of y_2 , the higher the relationship with the disease will be.

For illustration purposes, Table 1 shows an execution example using the largest dataset employed in this work with an epistasis size of 8 loci. This table shows the Pareto optimal solutions, specifically the eight SNPs of each solution and the values observed for the two objective functions. It is interesting to see that the SNP 6739 appears in all the Pareto optimal solutions. This means that this SNP could be very important in the phenotype occurrence of this dataset. Furthermore, it can be observed that when the value of y_1 decreases (it improves), the value of y_2 increases (it gets worse) and vice versa, demonstrating that both objective functions are conflicting each other.

Algorithm 1: NSGA-II Algorithm

Input : $popSize, MaxGen, crossProb, mutProb, mutRange$
Output: *ParetoFront* (set of non-dominated solutions)

```
1  $P \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2 for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $popSize$  do
3    $x_i \leftarrow \text{RandomIndividual}()$ 
4    $\text{EvaluateSolution}(x_i)$ 
5    $P \leftarrow P \cup x_i$ 
6 end
7  $P \leftarrow \text{FastNonDominatedSort}(P) // P = (F_{P1}, F_{P2}, \dots)$ 
8 for  $it \leftarrow 1$  to  $MaxGen$  do
9    $Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
10  for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $popSize/2$  do
11     $x_{p1}, x_{p2} \leftarrow \text{Selection}(P) // x_{p1} \neq x_{p2}$ 
12     $x_{q1}, x_{q2} \leftarrow \text{NewChildren}(x_{p1}, x_{p2}, crossProb, mutProb, mutRange)$ 
13     $\text{EvaluateSolution}(x_{q1})$ 
14     $\text{EvaluateSolution}(x_{q2})$ 
15     $Q \leftarrow Q \cup x_{q1} \cup x_{q2}$ 
16  end
17   $R \leftarrow \text{FastNonDominatedSort}(P \cup Q) // R = (F_{R1}, F_{R2}, \dots)$ 
18   $P \leftarrow \text{BestRankAndCrowdingSolutions}(R)$ 
19 end
20  $ParetoFront \leftarrow F_{P1}$ 
```

3. NSGA-II Proposal, Evolutionary Operators, and Parallelization

In this section we detail our approach to solve the tackled problem. Particularly, we provide insight into the characteristics of the chosen multi-objective metaheuristic (NSGA-II), the individual representation, the implemented evolutionary operators, and the proposed parallelization. We denominate our proposal as *NHOED* (NSGA-II for High-Order Epistasis Detection).

3.1. Fast Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II)

The fast Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm (NSGA-II) was introduced by Deb et al. in 2002 (Deb et al. (2002)) as an improvement of the original Non-Dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm. This algorithm employs two operators (crossover and mutation) to evolve a population of individuals seeking for the Pareto-optimal solutions of the problem, that is, the non-dominated solutions (Deb (2001)). Given two solutions x_1, x_2 , the dominance relationship ($x_1 \prec x_2$, that is, x_1 dominates x_2 or x_2 is dominated by x_1) for functions to be minimized is defined as shown in Equation

(6).

$$x_1 \prec x_2 \text{ if } \begin{cases} \forall i \in [1, n], y_i(x_1) \leq y_i(x_2) \\ \text{and} \\ \exists i \in [1, n], y_i(x_1) < y_i(x_2), \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

where n is the number of objective functions and y_i are the objective functions.

Algorithm 1 shows the pseudocode of NSGA-II. It takes as input the population size ($popSize$), the maximum number of generations that it will evolve ($MaxGen$), the crossover probability ($crossProb$), the mutation probability ($mutProb$) and the mutation range ($mutRange$), returning as output the found non-dominated solutions set ($ParetoFront$). These input parameters and problem-specific operators will be detailed in section 3.2. Now we describe the general procedure of the algorithm: First of all, the population P is initialized with $popSize$ randomly generated individuals (lines 1–6). Next, in line 7, the initial population is sorted by ranks using the dominance relationship and the fast non-dominated sort algorithm (Deb et al. (2002)), where the rank 1 is composed by non-dominated solutions, rank 2 is composed by solutions dominated only for those from rank 1, and so on. Then, the main loop is performed (lines 8–26) and repeated until the stop criterion is satisfied, in our case, a maximum number of generations. This loop involves the following steps:

- The first step is to generate a new population Q , that is, the offspring population (lines 9–16). In order to generate two new offspring individuals, two different parents are chosen from the parent population P (line 11) by using binary tournament selection (for every parent to be chosen, the best of two randomly taken individuals from P is selected). Then, two new children are created (line 12) using these two parents and the crossover and mutation operators. Finally, these new solutions are evaluated and added to the offspring population Q (lines 13–15). This process is repeated until Q has $popSize$ individuals.
- The second step is to join and sort by ranks both populations P and Q , resulting in a new combined population R of size $2 \times popSize$ (line 17).
- Finally, the best $popSize$ solutions of R are used to create the next parent population P (line 18), choosing first the solutions with the best ranks of R . Moreover, the crowding distance measurement is employed to sort the solutions of every rank according to the diversity. Due to

the *popSize* limitation, in case all the solutions of the last rank used cannot be chosen, the most diverse solutions will be selected.

Once the stop criterion is satisfied, the algorithm returns as output the set of non-dominated solutions, that is, the solutions with rank 1 (F_{P1}) from the last population P (line 27).

In addition, we are going to analyze the computational complexity of the NSGA-II algorithm using our problem-specific objective functions. For this purpose, we have defined the following elements: *popSize* is the population size (number of solutions in the population), S is the number of samples in the dataset, k is the epistasis size, *MaxGen* is the number of the iterations/generations performed by the algorithm, and M is the number of objective functions.

1. The first step is the initialization process. This is a loop of *popSize* iterations in which every new solution is created, with a complexity of $O(k)$, and evaluated by the two objective functions, where y_1 has a complexity of $O(3^k \times S)$ and y_2 has a complexity of $O(k)$. Therefore, because of the initialization process generates *popSize* solutions, it has a complexity of $O(\text{popSize} \times 3^k \times S)$.
2. The next step is the calculation of the rank of every individual. This procedure has a general complexity of $O(M \times \text{popSize}^2)$. In our case, because of $M = 2$, that is, a very small value, we can say that the rank calculation has a complexity of $O(\text{popSize}^2)$.
3. The last step is the main loop of the algorithm, which has *MaxGen* iterations. This loop is composed by the following steps:
 - (a) The offspring process, with a complexity of $O(\text{popSize} \times 3^k \times S)$.
 - (b) The rank calculation, with a complexity of $O(\text{popSize}^2)$.
 - (c) The crowding distance calculation, with a general complexity of $O(M \times \text{popSize} \times \log(\text{popSize}))$. As in the rank complexity, we can remove $M = 2$ from this complexity: $O(\text{popSize} \times \log(\text{popSize}))$.

Because of the number of samples (S) is, in general, higher than the population size (*popSize*), the main loop complexity is $O(\text{MaxGen} \times \text{popSize} \times 3^k \times S)$.

Therefore, the total complexity of our proposal is the same as its main loop, that is, $O(\text{MaxGen} \times \text{popSize} \times 3^k \times S)$.

3.2. Individual Representation and Evolutionary Operators

In the present work, the individual represents a k loci interaction. This means that a solution is encoded by a k -size vector where each element represents an SNP. Due to the fact that every SNP in the dataset is numbered

73	147
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73	147	896	1839	2047
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73	147	896	1839	2047	5796	8603	9756
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Figure 1: Individual representation with 2, 5 and 8 loci (from top to bottom)

from 0 to $N - 1$ (being N the number of SNPs in the dataset), the elements in the vector are given by unsigned integer numbers. Moreover, they have to satisfy the following restrictions: the elements in the vector must be sorted and one same SNP cannot be repeated within the same vector. Figure 1 graphically shows three individuals with 2, 5 and 8 loci (from top to bottom).

On the other hand, we have adapted the NSGA-II offspring generation process to address the high-order epistasis detection problem. More specifically, we have modified the crossover and mutation operators, as well as the children generation process. This new offspring generation process can achieve improved behaviour for this problem over previous approaches (Gallego-Sánchez et al. (2017)), as it will be seen in section 4.2.

3.2.1. Crossover Operator

For the crossover operator, we have implemented a single-point/double-point crossover. This operator generates two crossover points randomly between 0 and $k - 1$, which will be the reference SNPs to perform the crossover as shown in Equation (7).

$$\begin{aligned}
 c_1^i &= \begin{cases} p_1^i, & i < cp_1 \vee i > cp_2 \\ p_2^i, & i \geq cp_1 \wedge i \leq cp_2 \end{cases} \\
 \forall i \in [1, k], & \\
 c_2^i &= \begin{cases} p_2^i, & i < cp_1 \vee i > cp_2 \\ p_1^i, & i \geq cp_1 \wedge i \leq cp_2, \end{cases}
 \end{aligned} \tag{7}$$

where cp_1 and cp_2 are the crossover points, c_j^i is the SNP i from child j ($j \in [1, 2]$), and p_j^i is the SNP i from parent j ($j \in [1, 2]$). Table 2 presents all the possible situations that can happen when using these two crossover points.

Table 2: Crossover situations based on the value of the crossover points

Both points are different and in the range $[1, k - 2]$	Double-point crossover
Both points are different and one of them is 0	Single-point crossover
Both points are different and one of them is $k - 1$	Single-point crossover
Both points are equals	Single-point crossover

Figure 2: Crossover examples for individuals with $k = 7$ and $k = 2$. CP means “crossover point”.

On the other hand, $k = 2$ represents a special case because there are only two SNPs in the individual. In this case, only one-point crossover is performed by assigning 1 to both crossover points. Figure 2 shows examples for the four described situations of Table 2 and the especial case of $k = 2$.

Finally, it is noted that the crossover process is applied only when a random number between 0 and 100 is less or equal than the crossover probability. If this condition is not true, both children will be copies from their parents (in our case, the crossover function must return two children). The crossover probability is an input parameter of the application.

3.2.2. Mutation Operator

The mutation operator generates, for each SNP in the individual, a random number between 0 and 100. If this number is less or equal than the mutation probability, the currently processed SNP is assigned a randomly gen-

Algorithm 2: Offspring Generation Process (function NewChildren in Algorithm 1)

Input : $x_{p1}, x_{p2}, crossProb, mutProb, mutRange$
Output: x_{q1}, x_{q2}

```

1  $x_{q1}, x_{q2} \leftarrow Crossover(x_{p1}, x_{p2}, crossProb)$ 
2  $x_{q1} \leftarrow Mutation(x_{q1}, mutProb, mutRange)$ 
3  $x_{q2} \leftarrow Mutation(x_{q2}, mutProb, mutRange)$ 
4 if Not Crossover then
5   | if  $x_{q1}$  is not Mutated then  $x_{q1} \leftarrow RandomIndividual()$ 
6   | if  $x_{q2}$  is not Mutated then  $x_{q2} \leftarrow RandomIndividual()$ 
7 else
8   |  $Validate(x_{q1})$ 
9   |  $Validate(x_{q2})$ 
10 end
11 if  $IsEvaluated(x_{q1})$  then  $x_{q1} \leftarrow RandomIndividual()$ 
12 if  $IsEvaluated(x_{q2})$  then  $x_{q2} \leftarrow RandomIndividual()$ 
13  $MarkAsEvaluated(x_{q1})$ 
14  $MarkAsEvaluated(x_{q2})$ 

```

erated value that cannot be already present in the individual (as a same SNP cannot be repeated within the same individual). However, there is a limit in the range of SNPs that can be selected ($mutRange$). The range of SNPs that can substitute the SNP i is $[maximum(0, i - mutRange), minimum(i + mutRange, N - 1)]$, where N is the total number of SNPs. Finally, when all the individual's SNPs have been processed, the SNP values of the mutated individual must be sorted.

Now we provide insight into how the mutation probability and the mutation range values are obtained. The first one is calculated in accordance with the epistasis size (k) and an input parameter of the application: the lambda-mutation value ($\lambda mutation$). $\lambda mutation$ is a factor that increases or decreases the mutation probability ($\lambda mutation$ can take negative or positive values). Equation (8) shows how the mutation probability is calculated.

$$mutProb = \frac{100 + \lambda mutation}{k} \quad (8)$$

To calculate the mutation range, we employ the total number N of SNPs in the input dataset and a mutation factor $mutFactor$ (input parameter of the application), as shown in Equation (9).

$$mutRange = N \times \frac{mutFactor}{100} \quad (9)$$

3.2.3. The Offspring Generation Process

Next, we show in Algorithm 2 the complete process implemented to generate new individuals. This process involves the following steps:

- First of all, crossover and mutation are executed as described in the previous sections (lines 1–3).
- Afterwards, we check if each child is the result of the evolution process, that is, if the crossover or the mutation operators have been applied or not to generate that child (according to the crossover and mutation probabilities). In case that a child is not evolved, it is replaced by a new random individual (lines 4–6). On the other hand, if the crossover has been performed, the new individual could have two equal SNPs. To avoid this situation, the *Validate* function checks for repetitions of SNPs in one individual so that, if the function finds a repeated SNP, this SNP is increased until it is different from the rest of individual’s SNPs (lines 7–10).
- Finally, if the resulting child has already been generated in previous attempts, it is replaced by a randomly generated new individual (lines 11–12). These new individuals are marked as evaluated (lines 13–14). In order to detect which individuals have already been generated, the implementation stores all the evaluated individuals in a memory structure (being the maximum size of this memory structure equal to $MaxGen \times popSize \times k \times sizeof(integer)$ bytes).

3.3. Parallelization

Due to the large amount of data in the SNPs datasets, we have parallelized the NSGA-II algorithm. In order to perform accurately the parallelization of the code, we need to identify firstly which are the most time-consuming operations in the algorithm. After a time profile study, we found that the most computationally demanding operations in the algorithm are those involved in the individual generation and evaluation procedure, mostly because of the complexity of the two considered objective functions (as seen in sections 2.1 and 2.2).

Consequently, we have parallelized the two main sections in the algorithm related to the generation and evaluation of new individuals, that is, the initialization of the population (lines 2–6 of Algorithm 1) and the offspring generation step (lines 10–16 of Algorithm 1). In both cases, OpenMP has been employed to perform the parallelization, as can be seen in Algorithm 3. As shown in this algorithm, *numThreads* execution threads are spawned, so

Algorithm 3: Parallel NSGA-II Algorithm

```
Input : popSize, MaxGen, crossProb, mutProb, mutRange
Output: ParetoFront (set of non-dominated solutions)
1  $P \leftarrow \emptyset, Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2 #pragma omp parallel num_threads(numThreads)
3   #pragma omp for schedule(schedPolicy)
4     for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to popSize do
5        $x_i \leftarrow \text{RandomIndividual}()$ 
6       EvaluateSolution( $x_i$ )
7        $P \leftarrow P \cup x_i$ 
8     end
9   #pragma omp single
10     $P \leftarrow \text{FastNonDominatedSort}(P) // P = (F_{P1}, F_{P2}, \dots)$ 
11  for  $it \leftarrow 1$  to MaxGen do
12    #pragma omp for schedule(schedPolicy)
13      for  $i \leftarrow 1$  to  $\text{popSize}/2$  do
14         $x_{p1}, x_{p2} \leftarrow \text{Selection}(P) // x_{p1} \neq x_{p2}$ 
15         $x_{q1}, x_{q2} \leftarrow \text{NewChildren}(x_{p1}, x_{p2}, \text{crossProb}, \text{mutProb}, \text{mutRange})$ 
16        EvaluateSolution( $x_{q1}$ )
17        EvaluateSolution( $x_{q2}$ )
18         $Q \leftarrow Q \cup x_{q1} \cup x_{q2}$ 
19      end
20    #pragma omp single
21     $R \leftarrow \text{FastNonDominatedSort}(P \cup Q) // R = (F_{R1}, F_{R2}, \dots)$ 
22     $P \leftarrow \text{BestRankAndCrowdingSolutions}(R), Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
23  end
24 ParetoFront  $\leftarrow F_{P1}$ 
```

that each thread generates and evaluates new individuals in a parallel way through the directive `#pragma omp for` (taking advantage of the fact that these operations are independent from one individual to another). Moreover, the scheduler policy `schedPolicy` is set up from static and dynamic work assignment.

4. Experiments and Results

Once the tackled problem and the proposed approach have been described, we present now the obtained results. First of all, we explain the experimental methodology employed in this research. Then, the comparison between the traditional NSGA-II evolutionary operators and those implemented in this work are analyzed. Next, we undertake additional comparisons with the *MACOED* algorithm from Jing & Shen (2015), along with a biological comparison among *NHOED* and other methods. Finally, we conclude this section with the evaluation of parallel performance.

4.1. Experimental Methodology and Settings

This section shows the experimental methodology followed in this work. For experimentation purposes, we have employed a parallel infrastructure comprising AMD Opteron(tm) Abu Dhabi 6376 processors @2.30GHz (32 processing cores) with 96 GB of RAM, compiling the tested software by using g++ 4.9.3 on Ubuntu OS 14.04LTS. Moreover, the evaluation has been carried out over three types of datasets representing different problem sizes:

- 5,200 small datasets with 100 SNPs and 1,600 individuals generated under two biological models (DME, which displays both the interactive and marginal effects of the disease, and DNME, which displays only interactive and no marginal effects of the disease) and 52 penetrance tables (12 DME and 40 DNME) (Xie et al. (2012)). For every penetrance table there are 100 instances⁴.
- One medium size dataset with 1,000 SNPs and 4,000 individuals (2,000 controls and 2,000 cases)⁵.
- One large dataset with 31,341 SNPs and 146 individuals (50 controls and 96 cases)⁵.

All these datasets have been generated by means of GAMETES (Urbanowicz et al. (2012)). On the other hand, in order to ensure the statistical reliability of the comparisons, we have performed 31 executions of every algorithm and dataset.

In order to assess solution quality, we employ two well-known multi-objective metrics: Hypervolume (Beume et al. (2009)) and Set Coverage (Zitzler et al. (2003)). Considering two objectives, the first metric measures the area covered by a Pareto front with regard to a certain reference point. To calculate the Hypervolume of a Pareto front, this Pareto front is normalized by using the minimal and the maximal value of both objective functions (with an increment of 1%), taking into account all the executions from all the tested algorithms for the instance under analysis. Once the Pareto front is normalized, the Hypervolume score is calculated by using (1,1) as the reference point (both objective functions are to be minimized, so that is the nadir point). The second metric, Set Coverage (SC), is a binary-type indicator. It measures the percentage of solutions/points belonging to a Pareto

⁴These datasets can be downloaded from <http://www.csbio.sjtu.edu.cn/bioinf/MACOED/>.

⁵These datasets can be downloaded from <http://arco.unex.es/granado/SNP/>.

front B that are covered by solutions/points from another Pareto front A . If each solution in B is covered by at least one solution in A , then $SC(A, B)$ is equal to 1 (100%). Otherwise, if none of the solutions belonging to B is covered by the solutions in A , $SC(A, B)$ will be 0 (0%). Set Coverage is calculated as shown in Equation (10).

$$SC(A, B) = \frac{|\{b_j \in B; \exists a_i \in A : a_i \preceq b_j\}|}{|B|}, \quad (10)$$

where $|B|$ is the size (cardinality) of set B .

With respect to the configurations of the algorithms used in the comparisons, we have used the parameter values proposed by their authors (Jing & Shen (2015), Gallego-Sánchez et al. (2017)). In addition, we have performed a parametric study to conduct the configuration of *NHOED*. Uniformly-distributed combinations of parameters have been tested in order to obtain general values to use with any dataset. For the case of the crossover probability (*crossProb*), the mutation factor (*mutFactor*) and the lambda mutation (*lambdaMutation*), the range of values analyzed for each parameter is:

- *crossProb* \Rightarrow 40%, **50%**, 60%, 70%, 80%, 90%
- *mutFactor* \Rightarrow 10, 15, 20, 25, **30**, 35
- *lambdaMutation* \Rightarrow -20, -10, 0, 10, **20**, 30

The configuration chosen (data in bold) is the one that reported the best mean Hypervolumen, taking into account all the executions of all instances with that configuration. For the population size and the number of iterations, we started with 50 and 100 respectively for the smallest datasets, that is, 5,000 evaluations (same values as *MACOED*), 100 and 1,500 respectively for the 1,000 SNPs dataset (150,000 evaluations), and 500 and 2,000 (1,000,000 evaluations) for the largest dataset. For this purpose, we have performed a study to select the best pair of values for the largest dataset with $k = 8$ using 1,000,000 evaluations. In this way, all the compared algorithms are configured with the same population size and number of iterations than *NHOED* in order to perform fair comparisons.

Finally, for statistical validation purposes, we have applied the Kruskal Wallis test (Kruskal & Wallis (1952)) to check for statistically significant differences among the results generated by the methods and approaches under comparison (considering a confidence level of 95%).

Table 3: Set Coverage results between *NHOED* and *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*. We highlight in bold the best results in the comparison.

Dataset	k	SC(<i>NHOED</i> , <i>NSGA-II_{StdOps}</i>)	SC(<i>NSGA-II_{StdOps}</i> , <i>NHOED</i>)
1,000 SNPs	2	88.89%	75.00%
1,000 SNPs	5	100.00%	0.00%
1,000 SNPs	8	92.31%	21.43%
31,341 SNPs	2	75.00%	28.57%
31,341 SNPs	5	100.00%	0.00%
31,341 SNPs	8	100.00%	0.00%

Table 4: Hypervolume results, in format *median_{±quartile_deviation}*, and Kruskal-Wallis’ p-values of *NHOED* and *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*. We highlight in bold the best results in the comparison and the p-values denoting statistically significant differences.

Dataset	k	<i>NHOED</i>	<i>NSGA-II_{StdOps}</i>	p-value
1,000 SNPs	2	90.4%±0.024	89.2%±0.013	0.0019
1,000 SNPs	5	96.7%±0.005	95.7%±0.005	0.0212
1,000 SNPs	8	93.5%±0.007	92.9%±0.010	0.0228
31,341 SNPs	2	79.2%±0.017	69.2%±0.023	8.14E – 06
31,341 SNPs	5	69.9%±0.029	43.8%±0.026	3.24E – 11
31,341 SNPs	8	59.4%±0.034	32.0%±0.021	6.57E – 12

4.2. Evolutionary Operators Comparison

This section presents a comparison between the standard offspring process of *NSGA-II* (*NSGA-II_{StdOps}*) (Gallego-Sánchez et al. (2017)) and the *NSGA-II* with the proposed offspring process described in section 3.2 (*NHOED*). For the *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*, the crossover operator employed is the single-point crossover. This crossover chooses a point located at the individuals’ center and creates two new individuals joining the first part of the first individual with the second part of the second individual and vice versa. On the other hand, the mutation operator changes one SNP for another one in a certain range. Both operators take into account their respective probabilities.

As Tables 3 and 4 show, the offspring process of *NHOED* improves *NSGA-II_{StdOps}* in terms of both Set Coverage and Hypervolume for the 1,000 SNPs and the 31,341 SNPs dataset with $k = \{2, 5, 8\}$. Only for the 1,000 SNPs dataset and $k = 2$ the differences between both methods become closer, but *NHOED* still leads to a statistically significant improvement. On the other hand, when the dataset size and the k value are higher, the difference between both methods is more noticeable, attaining *NHOED* an increase of 85.5% in Hypervolume and a Set Coverage percentage of 100% for $k = 8$. This fact can be observed in Figures 3, 4 and 5, where the Pareto fronts from the median Hypervolume execution of these algorithms are represented. On comparing these fronts, Figure 3(a) points out that

(a) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 2$ in the medium size dataset.

(b) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 2$ in the largest dataset.

Figure 3: Median Pareto fronts for $k = 2$ in the medium and largest datasets.

(a) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 5$ in the medium size dataset.

(b) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 5$ in the largest dataset.

Figure 4: Median Pareto fronts for $k = 5$ in the medium and largest datasets.

(a) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 8$ in the medium size dataset.

(b) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 8$ in the largest dataset.

Figure 5: Median Pareto fronts for $k = 8$ in the medium and largest datasets.

Figure 6: Convergence for $k = 2$ using the largest dataset (31,341 SNPs and 146 individuals).

both methods are close (yet *NHOED* better) in the 1,000 SNPs dataset with $k = 2$, but when the epistasis size increases, *NHOED* improves *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*, as Figures 4(a) and 5(a) prove. Figure 3(b) shows that *NHOED* significantly improves *NSGA-II_{StdOps}* when the dataset size is increased, and Figures 4(b) and 5(b) give account of the fact that the fronts obtained by *NHOED* are considerably better than those obtained by *NSGA-II_{StdOps}* on increasing values of k . For all the considered datasets, Table 4 shows that there are statistically significant differences between both algorithms, with p-values below 0.023.

Finally, in Figure 6 we compare the convergence of both methods over the 31,341 SNPs dataset and $k = 2$. To perform this analysis, we have taken the intermediate results of both algorithms every 50 iterations. As it can be observed, both methods converge very fast in the first 150 iterations, achieving a Hypervolume of about 75% (*NHOED*) and 65% (*NSGA-II_{StdOps}*). However, as we can see *NHOED* continue improving its Hypervolume along the rest of iterations, while *NSGA-II_{StdOps}* remains at 67% Hypervolume from iteration 500 to 1,800. This means that *NHOED* has a lower stagnation behavior than *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*.

4.3. Comparison with Other Algorithms

This section presents a comparison between *NHOED* and *MACOED* (Jing & Shen (2015)). *MACOED* is a multi-objective algorithm based on ACO which solves the epistasis detection problem under the same objective functions considered in this work. This approach employs a k -dimensional matrix of N elements per dimension (where N is the number of SNPs in

Table 5: Hypervolume results from *NHOED* and *MACOED* for the smallest datasets, in format $mean \pm standard_deviation$. We highlight in bold the best results in the comparison.

ID	NHOED	MACOED	ID	NHOED	MACOED
0	71.0% ± 0.093	60.4% ± 0.267	30	64.4% ± 0.099	57.2% ± 0.205
1	67.0% ± 0.088	53.1% ± 0.274	31	62.1% ± 0.083	52.4% ± 0.207
2	73.4% ± 0.091	63.8% ± 0.253	32	65.3% ± 0.078	55.6% ± 0.208
3	71.9% ± 0.090	60.2% ± 0.275	33	73.8% ± 0.064	64.6% ± 0.211
4	69.7% ± 0.096	57.7% ± 0.262	34	70.6% ± 0.088	64.7% ± 0.188
5	59.3% ± 0.114	48.6% ± 0.232	40	65.8% ± 0.093	55.2% ± 0.225
6	54.3% ± 0.109	48.7% ± 0.192	41	73.8% ± 0.076	65.7% ± 0.188
7	68.1% ± 0.097	61.4% ± 0.204	42	65.2% ± 0.095	57.3% ± 0.203
8	61.5% ± 0.102	52.7% ± 0.215	43	74.1% ± 0.065	69.0% ± 0.136
9	66.4% ± 0.109	53.2% ± 0.259	44	72.2% ± 0.068	66.8% ± 0.140
15	59.7% ± 0.102	56.6% ± 0.130	55	77.0% ± 0.041	75.7% ± 0.039
16	64.4% ± 0.116	59.7% ± 0.153	56	66.9% ± 0.042	66.1% ± 0.041
17	68.0% ± 0.083	61.3% ± 0.151	57	78.0% ± 0.043	76.8% ± 0.043
18	69.6% ± 0.102	59.4% ± 0.192	58	65.5% ± 0.092	63.2% ± 0.093
19	63.0% ± 0.115	56.4% ± 0.180	59	82.0% ± 0.046	80.8% ± 0.043
25	68.4% ± 0.088	58.3% ± 0.244	65	75.6% ± 0.062	73.3% ± 0.074
26	66.1% ± 0.077	53.9% ± 0.238	66	73.8% ± 0.040	72.9% ± 0.042
27	72.2% ± 0.081	57.4% ± 0.293	67	66.9% ± 0.081	62.9% ± 0.117
28	73.0% ± 0.061	63.0% ± 0.239	68	74.8% ± 0.073	71.6% ± 0.082
29	66.2% ± 0.072	54.9% ± 0.244	69	65.9% ± 0.067	64.1% ± 0.072
70	84.0% ± 0.046	83.1% ± 0.047	76	55.9% ± 0.115	52.7% ± 0.131
71	84.8% ± 0.047	84.0% ± 0.047	77	63.2% ± 0.110	58.4% ± 0.126
72	78.3% ± 0.062	77.1% ± 0.061	78	67.8% ± 0.122	62.2% ± 0.157
73	78.5% ± 0.064	77.4% ± 0.064	79	60.3% ± 0.147	54.9% ± 0.179
74	72.3% ± 0.096	70.1% ± 0.108	80	67.9% ± 0.116	58.8% ± 0.185
75	57.0% ± 0.103	53.8% ± 0.118	81	63.3% ± 0.119	58.6% ± 0.136

(a) DNME

(b) DME

Figure 7: Number of instances in DNME and DME in which the obtained Hypervolume of *NHOED* is better or equal than *MACOED* for the smallest datasets (the red line represents the mean value).

the dataset) to store the objective functions values of the processed SNP combinations. This fact leads to memory consumption issues, thus making it impossible for *MACOED* to process epistasis sizes above $k = 2$. As an illustration, *MACOED* requires more than 43GB of RAM for the 31,341 dataset and $k = 2$. Therefore, we undertake the comparison with *MACOED* by using $k = 2$ configurations.

First of all, we have performed a comparative study with the smallest datasets, that is, 100 instances for each one of the 52 penetrance tables, 40 for the DNME model (IDs 0–69) and 12 for the DME model (IDs 70–81), where *ID* is the penetrance table identifier (same identifiers as those used in *MACOED*). Therefore, we have performed 100 executions for every penetrance table. As it can be observed in Table 5, the mean Hypervolumes from *NHOED* are better than *MACOED*'s for all penetrance tables under both DNME and DME models. Moreover, Figure 7 shows that *NHOED* is

Table 6: Kruskal-Wallis’ p-values of *NHOED* and *MACOED* for the smallest datasets. In bold we highlight the data with statistically significant differences.

ID	p-value	ID	p-value	ID	p-value	ID	p-value
0	0.0792	15	0.1611	30	0.0876	55	0.0078
1	0.0049	16	0.0559	31	0.0121	56	0.0579
2	0.0691	17	0.0065	32	0.0122	57	0.0148
3	0.0537	18	0.0018	33	0.0231	58	0.0429
4	0.0158	19	0.0238	34	0.1615	59	0.0562
5	0.0071	25	0.0454	40	0.0103	65	0.0348
6	0.2204	26	0.0052	41	0.0189	66	0.0223
7	0.1162	27	0.0380	42	0.0548	67	0.0384
8	0.0410	28	0.0667	43	0.0715	68	0.0067
9	0.0020	29	0.0351	44	0.0583	69	0.0384
70	0.0883	73	0.1397	76	0.0399	79	0.0271
71	0.1377	74	0.1125	77	0.0048	80	0.0016
72	0.0890	75	0.0183	78	0.0112	81	0.0135

Table 7: Set Coverage results between *NHOED* and *MACOED* for the medium and the largest datasets. We highlight in bold the best results in the comparison.

Dataset	SC(<i>NHOED</i> , <i>MACOED</i>)	SC(<i>MACOED</i> , <i>NHOED</i>)
1,000 SNPs	100.00%	25.00%
31,341 SNPs	100.00%	0.00%

better or equal in almost all the 5,200 instances under analysis. In order to further analyze these results, Table 6 presents p-values for every penetrance table. As it can be seen, there are statistically significant differences in 25 of the 40 DNME penetrance tables and in 7 of the 12 DME penetrance tables (data in bold). This is due to the fact that the optimal solutions are achieved many times under both algorithms in the rest of penetrance tables because the employed datasets are very small.

With regard to the medium and the largest datasets (we have performed 31 executions for both of them), we can observe in Table 7 that, when the size of the dataset is increased, all the solutions achieved by *MACOED* are covered by those obtained by *NHOED* in both datasets. Moreover, only 25% of the solutions achieved by *NHOED* are covered by those obtained by *MACOED* in the 1,000 SNPs dataset and none in the case of the 31,341 SNPs dataset. Accordingly, the Hypervolume obtained by *NHOED* is better than the obtained by *MACOED* for both datasets (Table 8). This fact is confirmed in Figures 8(a) and 8(b), where the Pareto fronts from the median Hypervolume execution of both algorithms are drawn. As it can be seen in these figures, *NHOED* has more solutions, coverage, spread, and diversity than *MACOED*. Moreover, statistically significant differences were found between both algorithms in these datasets, as shown in Table 8.

(a) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 2$ in the medium size dataset.

(b) Median Pareto fronts for $k = 2$ in the largest dataset.

Figure 8: Median Pareto fronts for $k = 2$ in the medium and largest datasets. Remember that *MACOED* cannot be applied in $k = 5$ and $k = 8$ due to memory issues.

Table 8: Hypervolume results, in format $median \pm quartile_deviation$, and Kruskal-Wallis’ p-value of *NHOED* and *MACOED* for the medium and the largest datasets. We highlight in bold the best results in the comparison and the p-values denoting statistically significant differences.

Dataset	NHOED	MACOED	p-value
1,000 SNPs	90.4%\pm0.024	83.9% \pm 0.013	5.09E – 06
31,341 SNPs	79.2%\pm0.017	37.7% \pm 0.023	1.33E – 07

Figure 9: Convergence for $k = 2$ using the largest dataset (31,341 SNPs and 146 individuals).

Finally, we compare the convergence of both algorithms in Figure 9 over the 31,341 SNPs dataset and $k = 2$. To perform this analysis, we have taken the intermediate results of both algorithms every 50 iterations. This figure shows that *NHOED* improves faster than *MACOED*, reaching in just 50 iterations a Hypervolume value that is almost twice the one achieved by *MACOED* in 2,000 iterations. In this case, *MACOED* does not suffer about stagnation (it improves its Hypervolume along all the 2,000 iterations), but its result is very far from the one obtained by *NHOED*.

4.4. Biological Comparison

Once we have compared *NHOED* in multi-objective terms, we now perform the biological assessment of the proposal. For this purpose, since biological metrics are used, we compare *NHOED* with different biological methods found in the literature, as well as *NSGA-II StdOps* and *MACOED*. These other biological methods are *AntEpiSeeker* (Wang et al. (2010)), *CSE* (Aflakparast et al. (2014)), *FHSA-SED* (Tuo et al. (2016)), Bayesian Epis-

tasis Association Mapping (*BEAM*)⁶ (Zhang & Liu (2007)), and Boolean Operation-based Screening and Testing (*BOOST*)⁷ (Wan et al. (2010)).

We have employed four well-known biological metrics to make these comparisons:

- Power (Equation (11)), which measures the number of times that the method finds the true disease-causing models ($\#S$) with respect to the total number of datasets ($\#T$).
- Recall (Equation (12)), which is the number of true positives (TP) found in the output divided by the total number of true positives, that is, true positives found (TP) plus false negatives (true positives not found, FN).
- Precision (Equation (13)), which is the number of true positives found (TP) divided by the total number of outputted values, that is, true positives found plus false positives (FP). This measurement is used to reflect the false positive rate of a method.
- F-measure (Equation (14)), which is a combining measurement between Recall and Precision.

$$Power = \frac{\#S}{\#T} \quad (11)$$

$$Recall = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (12)$$

$$Precision = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (13)$$

$$F\text{-measure} = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{Recall} + \frac{1}{Precision}} \quad (14)$$

To perform the biological study, after the *NHOED* execution, we execute an exhaustive search among all the SNPs in the non-dominated solutions, and then a Pearson χ^2 test (Pearson (1900)) is conducted. The Pearson χ^2 test is also a well-known method in the GWAS literature. In this way, only those solutions whose *p-value* is below a specific value (α) are selected. α

⁶<https://omictools.com/beam-tool>

⁷<http://bioinformatics.ust.hk/BOOST.html>

is calculated using the conservative Bonferroni correction based on an user-defined significance level (α_0), as Equation (15) shows. For α_0 we employ 0.1, the same value of *MACOED* and *FHSA-SED*.

$$\alpha = \frac{\alpha_0}{\binom{N}{k}}, \quad (15)$$

where N is the number of SNPs in the dataset and k is the epistasis size.

Table 9 shows the mean and standard deviation of the four biological metrics used in this study, comparing *NHOED* with other methods. The values of this table have been calculated using data reported in their corresponding papers. First of all, we have the power metric. As we can see, *NHOED* has a power of 0.89, a better result than *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*, *CSE* and *FHSA-SED*, this last one being the closest, but *NHOED* is better in terms of both mean and standard deviation. It is worth remarking that the entries with n/a in this column refer to methods that did not report specific power values in their corresponding papers.

The second metric is recall. In Table 9 we can see that *NHOED* has a recall value of 0.91, improving all the other biological methods under comparison. Again, the only method that is close to *NHOED* is *FHSA-SED*, but it has worse mean and standard deviation. In agreement with this metric we can conclude that *NHOED* and *FHSA-SED* have better tolerance to false negatives than the other methods.

In the next column, that is, precision, *NHOED* has better score than the other biological methods except *MACOED*, which has the same mean but worse standard deviation. Since both *NHOED* and *MACOED* have a high precision value, we can say that both methods are very tolerant to false positives.

Finally, for the last metric, f-measure, *NHOED* achieves the best value of all methods. As previously stated, f-measure is a combination of recall and precision. Therefore, *MACOED* and *FHSA-SED* have worse values than *NHOED* because they have good values in one metric but worse values in the another one.

In conclusion, we can say that *NHOED* is more accurate and tolerant than all the other methods in Table 9 with both false positives and false negatives, as shown by recall, precision, and f-measure. It is worth remarking that *CSE* method only reports if the disease-causing has been found or not, and it does not present any statistical analysis. For this reason, only its power value is presented in Table 9.

Table 9: Biological values of Power, Recall, Precision, and F-measure metrics of *NHOED* compared with several methods found in the literature. Data are presented in format $mean \pm standard_deviation$. Bold values with dark gray background represent the best ones and values with light gray background are the second ones. *n/a* represents values that are not presented in their corresponding paper.

Method	Power	Recall	Precision	F-measure
<i>NHOED</i>	0.89\pm0.20	0.91\pm0.14	0.95\pm0.11	0.93\pm0.13
<i>MACOED</i> (Jing & Shen (2015))	<i>n/a</i>	0.84 \pm 0.31	0.95\pm0.12	0.86 \pm 0.28
<i>AntEpiSeeker</i> (Wang et al. (2010))	<i>n/a</i>	0.77 \pm 0.31)	0.91 \pm 0.17	0.81 \pm 0.28
<i>BOOST</i> (Wan et al. (2010))	<i>n/a</i>	0.82 \pm 0.32	0.54 \pm 0.18	0.65 \pm 0.23
<i>NSGA-II_{StdOps}</i> (Gallego-Sánchez et al. (2017))	0.67 \pm 0.20	0.72 \pm 0.17	0.46 \pm 0.35	0.50 \pm 0.31
<i>BEAM</i> (Zhang & Liu (2007))	<i>n/a</i>	0.07 \pm 0.20	0.14 \pm 0.20	0.08 \pm 0.19
<i>CSE</i> (Aflakparast et al. (2014))	0.20 \pm 0.05	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>	<i>n/a</i>
<i>FHSA-SED</i> (Tuo et al. (2016))	0.88\pm0.25	0.90\pm0.25	0.93\pm0.12	0.90\pm0.21

4.5. Parallel Study

In this section we conduct a parallel performance study to analyze the scalability of our proposal. We have employed four system configurations (8, 16, 24, and 32 cores), two scheduling policies (static and dynamic) and three values of k (2, 5, and 8) on the largest dataset. In this section, due to the high execution times of the problem, we have performed 11 executions per configuration for both *NSGA-II_{StdOps}* and *NHOED* algorithms. Figure 10 shows the median efficiency and speed up of these executions. As it can be observed, the dynamic scheduling approach behaves better than the static version in all the considered cases. This is due to the fact that the objective functions show different execution time requirements, thus motivating a better exploitation of hardware resources when dynamic scheduling policies are employed. Focusing on the two tested algorithms, we can see that *NHOED* has better efficiency and speed up than *NSGA-II_{StdOps}* in almost all configurations. Only for 8 and 32 cores with $k = 8$ (Figures 10(e) and 10(f)) *NHOED* does not improve *NSGA-II_{StdOps}*, yet similar performance is attained.

Table 10 shows the execution time for every configuration. We can observe that, by using *NHOED*, the execution time is reduced from 2.2 hours to 5.4 minutes for $k = 2$, from 3.3 hours to 9.8 minutes for $k = 5$, and from 4.9 hours to 17.4 minutes for $k = 8$. These results suggest that the proposal allows the solution of high-order epistasis problems with large datasets in a reasonable time. Finally, by comparing the data of Table 10 with the execution time of *MACOED* (it needs 1,535.3 seconds to process the 31,341 SNPs dataset with $k = 2$), we can observe that *MACOED* is faster than *NHOED* for the sequential execution thanks to the memory structure that allows

(a) Efficiency for $k = 2$.

(b) Speed Up for $k = 2$.

(c) Efficiency for $k = 5$.

(d) Speed Up for $k = 5$.

(e) Efficiency for $k = 8$.

(f) Speed Up for $k = 8$.

Figure 10: Efficiency and Speed Up using the 31,341 SNPs dataset, $k = \{2, 5, 8\}$, and static ($_{st}$) and dynamic ($_{dy}$) scheduling for *NHOED* and *NSGA-II $_{StdOps}$* .

Table 10: Median execution time in seconds. Comparisons between *NHOED* and *NSGA-II*_{StdOps}

Implementation	k	Number of threads				
		1	8	16	24	32
NHOED _{st}	2	7,893.97	1,080.12	607.36	457.02	346.82
NHOED _{dy}			1,011.69	553.16	419.75	321.30
NSGA-II StdOps _{st}		9,237.36	1,457.05	866.66	605.66	520.47
NSGA-II StdOps _{dy}			1,415.18	806.36	557.23	470.83
NHOED _{st}	5	11,803.79	1,795.49	1,047.92	864.47	642.85
NHOED _{dy}			1,510.24	837.97	657.37	587.56
NSGA-II StdOps _{st}		11,256.01	1,858.73	1,131.37	928.58	834.22
NSGA-II StdOps _{dy}			1,637.72	1,019.37	764.01	671.56
NHOED _{st}	8	17,519.64	2,730.63	1,548.88	1,281.53	1,223.66
NHOED _{dy}			2,226.11	1,313.85	1,111.44	1,041.51
NSGA-II StdOps _{st}		16,835.74	2,160.77	1,599.08	1,379.49	1,279.86
NSGA-II StdOps _{dy}			2,118.84	1,442.97	1,103.21	989.72

MACOED to store the already calculated objective function values (please observe that *MACOED* needs more than 43GB of RAM for this dataset with $k = 2$). However, *NHOED* with only 8 cores already improves the execution time of *MACOED*. This means that *NHOED* offsets the expensive memory requirements of *MACOED* by using only 8 cores, thus being able to manage larger datasets and epistasis sizes than *MACOED* (for $k = 3$ and the 31,341 SNPs, *MACOED* would need more than 671TB of RAM).

5. Discussion

This work presents a multi-objective implementation for solving the high order epistasis detection problem using the NSGA-II algorithm, parallelism and a problem-aware offspring process. First of all, the evolutionary algorithm evolves the initial population to obtain a Pareto optimal solution set. After that, a decision making process is performed by the Pearson χ^2 test among all the SNPs combinations that can be formed using all the SNPs that are included in the Pareto optimal set. After this decision making process, we will have the SNP interactions with p-values under a specific threshold, which will be the final solutions.

Some limitations in the proposed approach are examined below:

1. Even though our proposal is very parallelizable, that is, the whole offspring process can be calculated in parallel as the complete execution of this procedure has no data dependencies, the population ranking and management tasks is strictly sequential due to data dependencies issues. This means that, after each parallel offspring generation, the invocation of this function carries out a sequential blocking. Although

the execution time of this function is not very high, the mentioned sequential blocking can have an impact in the efficiency of our proposal, contributing to the overall serial fraction of the application.

2. The objective functions used in this work have demonstrated to obtain very good results. However, the logistic regression used to calculate the Akaike Information Criterion employs an additive-interactive model. In our experiments, this model has shown a good behavior, improving other works found in the literature, but other models could be checked in the future.

Now, let us compare the presented proposal with previous approaches to measure the value efficiency. Comparing to previous methods, we could state that the following advantages are considered:

1. The method suggested in this article presents a multi-objective proposal for solving the high-order epistasis detection problem. We have proven that the presented method improves other works found in the literature in both multi-objective and biological results.
2. By comparing our proposal with the NSGA-II algorithm using a standard offspring process, we have shown that the problem-specific offspring method designed in this work improves the original one. This proposed offspring process does not limit the parts that every new individual takes from its parents, both in terms of position and size of every part that a new individual takes from its parents, allowing the generation of more diverse solutions. This means that the proposed implementation explores more regions of the search space.
3. On comparing our proposal with *MACOED*, we can state that *NHOED* has better behavior in order to detect loci relationships. Because *MACOED* and *NHOED* have the same objective functions, the improvement of *NHOED* is due to the enhanced capabilities of the algorithm and the proposed search strategies. Moreover, our design takes better advantage of hardware resources, allowing the analysis of larger epistasis interaction orders (we have used eight as the highest order in our experiments but our implementation is not limited to this value), instead of the only order of two that *MACOED* (and other methods like *FHSA-SED*) allows.
4. Finally, we have performed a biological comparison with other works, including mono-objective proposals (*AntEpiSeeker* and *CSE*), multi-objective proposals (*MACOED* and *FHSA-SED*) and other well-known tools to solve this problem (*BEAN* and *BOOST*). In order to perform

to perform this comparison, we have employed four standard biological metrics in this area: Power, Recall, Precision, and F-measure. Our proposal improves all the other methods in all the employed metrics. As the used metrics measure the number of times that the optimal solution is found (Power) and the incidence of false positives (Recall) and false negatives (Precision), we can say that the proposed method attains very good quality, identifying more optimal solutions with less false positives and false negatives than the other works.

6. Conclusions and Future Work

This paper has provided insight into *NHOED*, a multi-objective optimization approach for addressing the high-order epistasis detection problem. This problem is aimed at finding the relationship between the occurrence of a disease and the presence of several SNPs in an individual (epistasis). More specifically, our proposal is able to handle epistasis sizes of 2, 5, and 8 loci, but higher values could also be considered (there is no epistasis size limit in the implementation). In addition, the proposal tackles the problem from a multi-objective perspective, where two objective functions are involved: AIC and Bayesian K2 score. To attain improved accuracy, we have developed and integrated into NSGA-II an offspring process that addresses the requirements of this problem. In order to validate our implementation, we have used multiple datasets: the first one containing 100 instances of 52 penetrance tables from two models (DNME and DME), that is, 5200 instances, each one with 100 SNPs and 1,600 patients; the second one with 1,000 SNPs and 4,000 patients; and the third one with 31,341 SNPs and 146 patients.

The proposed approach improves the results obtained by the reference method *MACOED* in terms of Hypervolume and Set Coverage in all datasets for an epistasis size of 2 (representing this value the only epistasis size supported in *MACOED*). Furthermore, *NHOED* allows the processing of larger datasets and epistasis sizes than *MACOED*, which would require an overwhelming amount of RAM to analyze large datasets and epistasis sizes (more than 671TB of RAM for $k = 3$ and 31,341 SNPs). In addition, we have examined the proposed *NHOED* offspring process by comparing it with NSGA-II under standard operators. By using this offspring process, *NHOED* is able to outperform NSGA-II with standard operators in terms of Hypervolume and Set Coverage for the two largest datasets.

Moreover, a biological study has been performed to compare *NHOED* with other methods found in the literature. We have employed four well-

known metrics to measure the quality of our proposal, that is, power, recall, precision and f-measure. These metrics have proved that *NHOED* has better tolerance to false positives and false negatives than the rest of the method. In this way, only *MACOED* and *FHSA-SED* are close to our results, but only in some of the metrics (*MACOED* in precision and *FHSA-SED* in recall and power), and they always have worse values.

Finally, a parallel study has been performed over system configurations of 8, 16, 24, and 32 cores, two scheduling policies, and three epistasis sizes (2, 5, and 8). According to the results of this study, we can conclude that *NHOED* has a good parallel performance under dynamic scheduling policies in all the considered evaluation scenarios. In this sense, *NHOED* also improves NSGA-II with standard operators in terms of parallel efficiency.

As future work, we will employ other multi-objective algorithms to compare them with *NHOED*. Specifically, we plan to implement an NSGA-III Deb & Jain (2014) version of our proposal, with the aim of evaluating the performance attained under the alternative optimization strategies adopted in its algorithmic design along with its potential parallelism. Moreover, we will use other real and larger datasets, along with integrating other objective functions into the proposal. We will also study to implement a parallel improvement of the population ranking and management procedures.

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Highlights

- The high-order epistasis detection problem is an important task in biomedicine
- This task can be tackled as a two-objective optimization problem
- We have designed a problem-aware evolutionary offspring process
- The experiments have been done over different datasets and epistasis sizes
- The proposal improves other methods in both multi-objective and biological terms